

Interactive Visualization to understand COVID Risk Score at a Particular Location using Tableau

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Abstract:- A lot has happened in the last few years since the World Health Organization declared COVID-19 as a global pandemic. Forcing every business to change the way they work to survive in this changing world. However, even though the lockdown slowed everything, still a huge amount of data continued to climb with speed and big data grew and become even bigger. As the world was changing and businesses were struggling to find new innovative ways and methods to continue doing business, data, and data analytics have provided a path of light. In this paper, an overview has been provided about Tableau a data analytics and visualization tool, which can crunch massive amounts of data and can provide hidden insights and trends through visual solutions that can be used by organizations to make quick business decisions. I have used Tableau to generate interactive visualizations to provide a solution for the Biotech/ pharma/ healthcare industries about an improved method of doing peer-to-peer engagements. As the Covid infection rate is going down and businesses are opening, it is important for the healthcare industry to understand the risk due to COVID before engaging with HCPs (health care professionals) in a live setting and doing peer to peer programs. COVID-19 open-source data has been utilized to provide the real-time COVID impact in a geographical location with accuracy, which could be monitored by companies to prepare for possible face-to-face engagements and find quick and innovative solutions to continue to make effective healthcare decisions.

Keywords:- Data, Visualization, Interactive Visualization, COVID-19, Tableau, Tableau Geocoding.

I. INTRODUCTION

As a very needed integral process for the Pharmaceutical/ Biotech industry, companies run a lot of HCP-related peer-to-peer programs, which are face-to-face meetings, conventions, and conferences to educate the HCPs (Health Care professionals) about the company's drug and different scientifically proven and approved treatment options [1]. During COVID all the interactions and companywide conferences went virtual, even one-to-one field sales reps/ KOL (Key Opinion Leader)/ MSL (Medical Science Liaison)& HCP meetings became virtual, which impacted the business. Today when life is slowly going back to normal, and

as the COVID infection rate is going down and businesses are opening, it is important for the healthcare industry to understand the risk score due to COVID before engaging with HCPs in a live setting and for doing peer to peer programs. This paper uses publicly available COVID infection data and census bureau population data [6,7] together to present a model to calculate whether a particular location in the US is safe or unsafe to have a face-to-face meeting. This is an interactive visualization created using Tableau as a business intelligence tool.

II. INTERACTIVE DATA VISUALIZATION

Data visualization is the presentation of data or information in a visual format such as a graph, chart, diagram, etc. Today ever-increasing data volumes are making already multifaceted big data even bigger and more complex. As a result, sorting, cleaning, comprehending, and explaining a huge amount of data is becoming more and more slow and difficult. This is where, to make data-driven decisions quickly and confidently and in real-time, data visualization has come into play. It provides the fastest and most effective way to interpret large batches of data and communicate pertinent details and insights by creating compelling, informative, beautiful, and eye-catching dashboards. The visualization uses human's natural skills to perceive and process visual information with higher efficiency compared to tabular data format [8]. It helps to monitor and deal with complex information at a glance and enhances memory [8], significantly helping to communicate messages more effectively. However, visualizations are static by nature and are used to publish materials such as publishing in print or online or for presentation purposes rather than exploration. Thus, it makes a difference when viz are created using interactive dashboards. Interactive data visualization being a powerful tool in the current age reaches beyond the limits of static dashboards. It converts static presentations into interactive sessions and makes the dashboards dynamic and empowers the users to interact with the data and discover patterns and trends by filtering the data on-demand or by simply clicking to drill down into the underlying data to gain quality insights in real-time.

III. METHODS

A. Installing Tableau Desktop for the Viz Creation:

a) Quick Introduction to Tableau:

Tableau is a user-friendly reporting/ analytics platform, which is used to develop dynamic reporting and analytics solutions for business users through high-quality visualizations. It is a cutting-edge visualization tool that empowers people and users to analyze and understand their data, and to quickly find insights and key trends to improve the overall decision-making process.

This is a unique software that cleans and blends data and presents the data in a meaningful visual format with worksheets, dashboards, and stories. It's a tool known for its many features such as simplicity, that is a non-technical user can easily master it as well as any technical user be it a beginner, intermediate, or an expert can learn and create visual analytics of different capacities, complexity, and depth. Along with this, it is known for its scale, that is, it can handle huge data sets and can connect to various data sources [2]. This functionality to pull data from multiple data sources provides it a significant advantage over other similar tools in the market. Starting from simple excel it can

connect to complex databases and data warehouses such as AWS [3] as well as web analytics services like Google Analytics. This paper has used AWS Redshift as one of the data sources connected to Tableau, to fetch data.

b) Installing Tableau Desktop:

Tableau Desktop: This is the design tool, generally installed in the local system to create dashboards and visual analytics. It's a licensed software. Tableau provides 2 weeks of trial and then the license needs to be purchased after the trial completion [4]. It includes:

- Personal Edition
- Professional Edition

The professional edition is an enterprise edition that has the functionality to connect to a much broader variety of data sources as compared to the personal edition [2]. The personal edition was designed with less functionality and can connect to only flat files and the generated report could only be saved to the local system or to Tableau Public. Unlike the professional edition, the reports/ dashboards created in the personal edition cannot be published to Tableau Online or to the Tableau server [2].

Fig. 1: Tableau Desktop – Data Pane

Installing the Tableau desktop is a simple and quick process. It could be installed in both Windows and MACs systems. In either of the systems at least 1.5 GB of free hard disk space would be needed [5] to install the tableau software. The given link could be used to download the latest trial version [10]: <https://www.tableau.com/products/desktop>.

Once the download is complete, depending on the browser the downloaded file could be located.

On a windows system, the downloaded EXE file is clicked and opened and after accepting the necessary prompts the installation would begin. And on a MAC system, the DMG file would be opened and the PKG installation package would be double-clicked to start the installation. After the installation

is complete, Tableau must be opened, and the user needs to complete the registration form to activate the Tableau Desktop installation. Users can get a 14-days free trial [10]. Tableau also provides a 1-year free product key for students and instructors. Below links could be used to provide necessary academic enrollment proof and after verification, a 1-year product key could be obtained, which could be used for a full year to access all the features of the software.

For Students [11]: <https://www.tableau.com/academic/students>

For Instructors [12]: <https://www.tableau.com/academic/teaching>

For this analysis, the Tableau Desktop (64 Bit) software is installed in the windows system.

IV. DATA PREPARATION

The data for this paper is collected from the public domain. Two separate datasets have been used, first is the publicly available COVID infection data. The data is released and updated in real-time by the New York times and provided in 3 separate CSVfiles for 3 geographical areas: US, States, and Counties [6]. The counties file is the most detailed file including the state and country columns as well. Unlike the other 2 files, which are aggregated data sets. Second is the US census bureau population data from the U.S. Census Bureau website [7].

Only the COVID infection counties file is downloaded from the website (in CSV format). A table is created in AWS Redshift and the file is uploaded to the table in this data warehouse. A script is created to load this data daily into the Redshift table, which is then automatically refreshed in the Tableau Dashboard. Figure2 shows the table in Redshift with the COVID data uploaded from the Web.

date	county	state	fips	cases	deaths
2022-05-09	Ellis	Kansas	20051	7151	84
2022-05-09	Elk	Kansas	20049	571	10
2022-05-09	Amherst	Virginia	51009	7300	88
2022-05-09	Amelia	Virginia	51007	2672	60
2022-05-09	Surry	North Car	37171	21149	350

Fig. 2: COVID Infection Data in a long table format in Redshift.

The COVID table in Redshift is connected to Tableau through the Tableau server connector. Figure 3 shows the Tableau connector page, with a list of a variety of common files and server types from which Tableau could be connected to pull data.

Fig. 3: Tableau Desktop Connector page showing a variety of basic file and server types

For this data set, “Amazon Redshift” under “To a Server” is selected and clicked. This opens a window shown in figure 4 to input credentials and other details about the server. A live connection is established after entering the server and

login details. And all the schemas and tables in the data warehouse could be seen in the data source pane in Tableau Desktop. From where the COVID table is dragged and dropped into the data connection section.

Fig. 4: Window Box to enter Connection details to connect to the AWS Redshift Datawarehouse

The population data is also downloaded as a CSV file from the US Census Bureau website. The demographic data is updated weekly on this government website. This excel file is connected to Tableau directly. The above Figure 3 shows the list. In this case “Microsoft Excel” under “To a File” is selected, which opens a dialog box that shows the excel supported files in the local system. The dialog box helps to navigate to the excel file and after the selection, Tableau establishes a live connection with the file.

A. Tableau Data Join

Tableau now is connected to 2 different data sets from two different data sources, it offers the option to combine/ join both the data sets using the common field present in both. As figure 6 shows, both the tables are joined using inner join using the ‘COUNTY’ column which is the county id present in both the datasets. Join being a robust function, once created, it will exist in the entire workbook and any number of worksheets or dashboards could be created using the combined data set.

Fig. 6: Tableau Data Source pane where both the data sets were joined using the unique column.

Once the combined data set is ready, a worksheet is opened which is the development area in tableau to create visualizations. In the worksheet we can see, Tableau has automatically differentiated the columns as dimensions and measures shown in Figure 7. It also gives the option to the

users to validate the data types already selected by Tableau for each column. Users can change the field data types as well as move the columns from Dimension to Measure pane or vice versa depending on the need.

Fig. 7: Tableau Development worksheet area, where columns from the data sets are automatically added into the dimensions and measures pane

B. Tableau Geocoding

Tableau geocoding is another excellent feature provided by Tableau. Tableau can geocode from 8 different types of geographic information such as fields like country, state, province, city, postal codes, etc. plus Latitude & Longitude coordinates. The geographic field is denoted by a small globe icon. Tableau automatically generates the longitude and latitude values for the center points of each geographic entity displayed in the visualization [2,4]. Along with it, users can also customize geocodes by assigning latitude and longitude coordinates to their locations so Tableau can plot them accurately on a map. In this paper, a filled map is used to create the visual dashboard.

per 100K population. The 3 categories are used to create another calculated column to divide the categories into 3 color segments based on the below definitions and the field is named 'Risk Category'.

- A. COVID Risk Score Definitions for colored risk categories:*
- High Risk → Red Color → **COVID Risk Score >100**
COVID Cases in the last 7 days Per 100K Population
 - Medium Risk → Yellow Color → **COVID Risk Score between 40 and 100** COVID Cases in the last 7 days Per 100K Population
 - Low Risk → Green Color → **COVID Risk Score <40** COVID Cases in the last 7 days Per 100K Population.

V. RISK SCORE MODELLING

The first data set used is the open-source COVID infection data, the last 7 days' worth of data has been uploaded into the Redshift table and connected to Tableau through the AWS Tableau connector. The 2nd data set is the US census bureau data for population details, which is connected to Tableau through the excel file. Both the data sets are joined using the unique county column present in both the data sets. Finally, a calculated column named 'COVID risk score' is created by calculating the last 7 days of new COVID cases per 100K population in a county (Figure 8). The risk scores are divided into 3 categories- high, medium, and low risk based on the number of COVID cases in the last 7 days

Fig. 8: COVID Risk Score logic.

VI. RESULTS

A. Basic View

A horizontal bar chart is created to show the risk score for each state by county. First, the fields 'State' and 'County' in the 'Dimensions' pane are dragged and dropped into the 'Rows' shelf. As these are the dimension fields, they are displayed in blue color. Then the 'COVID Risk Score' field

under the 'Measures' pane is dragged and dropped into the 'Columns' shelf. This field is displayed in green, and tableau automatically denotes it with the default aggregate function 'sum' as it is a numeric field, which can be changed based on the users' needs such as max, min, etc. This shows the risk score for each of the counties in a bar graph (Figure 9).

Fig. 9: Tableau desktop worksheet showing the horizontal Bar chart for the selected fields.

B. Filtering the view & understanding the highest risk score

Figure 9 is showing all the data for all the fields that have been dragged and dropped into the view. Now, the view could be enhanced with interactive features by using filters and mark cards. For the filters, 'State', 'County', and 'Risk Category' fields from the Dimensions pane are dragged and dropped into the 'Filters' shelf. Next, the 'Risk Category' is dropped into the 'Color' of the mark cards, followed by 'COVID Risk Score', 'COVID Cases', and 'Total Population' fields dragged

and dropped from the Dimensions pane into the 'Label' of the mark cards as highlighted below in Figure 10. This development area worksheet could now be moved into a formal dashboard section. Figure 11 is an example of the visual dashboard where some filters have been applied. The fields on the 'Label' would help to create the hover information, that is when the mouse hovers over a bar, it shows additional information in a pop-up box about the selected bar as shown in Figure 11.

Fig. 10: Highlights the Filter and Mark card shelves used to enhance the visualization.

Fig. 11: Example of filtering and showing the features of Mark Card in a dashboard.

C. Building a map view

The view is created using the tableau generated latitude and longitude coordinates along with the state column from the data set. In the tableau development area, a new worksheet is selected and the field ‘State’ from the Dimensions pane is dragged and dropped into the ‘Detail’ of the mark cards. Tableau automatically drags and drops Longitude and Latitude fields from the ‘Measures’ pane on the ‘Columns’ and ‘Rows’ shelves respectively and creates a map. ‘Show me’ shows 2 options for map view filled or symbol. In this case, the Filled map is selected for the visualization. ‘State’ is added to the filter shelf like in the previous view. For the quantitative measure, both the ‘COVID Risk Score’ and total ‘COVID Cases’ are to be shown on the map by State. So, a parameter ‘COVID Metric’ is created to toggle between 2 measures

‘COVID Risk Score’ and ‘COVID Cases’. This parameter is used to create a calculated column ‘Metric’ (Figure 12), which is dragged and dropped onto the ‘color’ of the mark cards. Then the color in the mark card is selected and from the color list ‘Red-Blue’ diverging is selected, and ‘Reversed’ is checked. So, that high score or high cases would show in red color and the reverse would show in blue color. Figure 13 is showing the visualization with the parameter filter ‘COVID Metric’ where the current default selection is ‘COVID Risk Score’ (i.e., New COVID infection cases in the last 7 days per 100K population in the state) and the map is shaded with the risk score numbers for each state. The color shading for the states in the map is changed when the parameter filter is changed to the ‘COVID Cases’ to show the total COVID cases in the last 7 days by State.

Fig. 12: Steps for creating the Map view.

Fig. 13: Filled Map with US states shaded according to the sum of either COVID Cases or COVID Risk score based on the metric selected in the ‘COVID Metric’ filter.

VII. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

By following some of the steps and processes in Tableau, described in the paper, it would be possible to create simple views by using small and medium-sized sample data sets for beginners. However, experts in the tool can use Tableau to its full potential and can create various visualizations such as graphs, pie charts, bubble charts, highlight tables, heat maps, symbols maps, filled maps, tree maps, and many more. As well as can use trend and reference lines for complex analytical dashboarding. Along with it, visualizations could be customized based on business users’ needs and requirements. Every visualization could be optimized by incorporating interactive features into it such as using multiple filters at a time to drill down through the data, adding dashboard actions to create relationships between worksheets in a dashboard, creating calculated customized columns, and so on. Tableau also provides a great layout feature that allows the creation of visualizations and dashboards for other electronic media such as mobile phones and tablets [15]. Giving the advantage to field users in different industries who generally spend most of their time outside office premises at client or customer locations or users working in a fast pace working environment away from a normal office set up, to access real-time data through viz and dashboards on phones and tablets with ease and flexibility[15]. The right device preview could be selected

during report and dashboard creation, which would automatically recognize the device user is using and changes the size of the report by making proper adjustments to ensure that the report is shared on the device screen appropriately. Additionally, Tableau also provides opportunities to discover data patterns and can be used for advanced analytics through machine learning algorithms. Intermediate and advanced level visualization details would be covered in a future paper.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Users’ ability to perceive data is enhanced significantly when data or information is presented in a visual format. It becomes difficult to miss out on important insights. Visual display of data always would have a significant advantage over regular tabular format data. And in today’s post COVID world, industries are showing a great interest in data analytics through visualizations. Tableau being a powerful visual analytics tool, could be used to create impactful visualizations by harnessing a massive amount of data through various data sources, which could help users to see, understand as well as explore the data. It is loaded with user-friendly and state-of-the-art features and world-class functionalities which could help to extract valuable insights, which could be analyzed through interactive visualizations. In this paper, I used data from 2 different data sources and merged them together in the

Tableau layer to perform the data analysis and create interactive visual dashboards.

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